

cyclisation has been now effected by modifying the method.

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide dissolved in acetic acid was refluxed but failed to yield the cyclised product. On using a solution of sulphuric acid in acetic acid and subsequently boiling the compound obtained was found to be the pyrazoline derivative. This was also obtained by boiling in ethanol a mixture of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, mesityl oxide and sulphuric acid.

Evidence for the cyclisation is as follows: Chemical tests viz., the Knorr colour test⁶ failed to give the expected colours but is known to fail^{1,7}, and reduction with sodium-amalgam/ethanol⁸⁻¹⁰ could not be carried out due to insolubility of the compound. Hence in spectral analyses the N-H stretch absorption peak in the I.R. region is the only conclusive evidence that could be used to distinguish the pyrazoline derivative from the hydrazone¹⁰. The I.R. spectra of this product shows no absorption band around the frequency 3000 cm^{-1} i.e., the N-H group is absent and therefore cyclisation has taken place.

Experimental

The preparation of 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-2-pyrazoline has been carried out in two ways:

(a) Cyclisation of the hydrazone to the pyrazoline:

To 0.5 g. of the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide was added 15 ml of glacial acetic acid and 0.4 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid, also 2-3 drops of water. This was refluxed for 3 hrs. On cooling the compound obtained was washed with water and leached with boiling alcohol. Recrystallised from glacial AcOH. M.p. 295°.

(b) Direct preparation of the pyrazoline from 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine:

One gram of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine was dissolved in EtOH (100 ml). To this was added 5 ml of mesityl oxide and 2.0 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 . It was refluxed vigorously for 5-6 hrs. This was allowed to cool and filtered, the residue was washed successively with hot water, hot acetone and hot alcohol. Recrystallised from pure AcOH. Orange red crystals. M.p. 295°.

This compound was found to be insoluble in ethanol, acetone, ether, benzene, dioxane and water.

Analysis: $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$

	%C	%H	%N
Requires	51.99	4.69	20.21
Found	52.07	4.83	20.17

3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-2-pyrazoline.

References

1. KV. AUWERS and A. KREUDER, *Ber.*, 1925, 58B, 1974.
2. KV. AUWERS and H. VOSS, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4412.
3. C. F. H. ALLEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 51, 2957.
4. C. F. H. ALLEN and J. H. RICHMOND, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 2, 222.
5. J. D. ROBERTS and C. GREEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 214.
6. KNORR, *Ann.*, 1887, 238, 200.
7. C. J. F. VAZ and J. MISQUITTA, (unpublished work).
8. L. C. RAIFORD and G. V. GUNDY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 265.
9. L. C. RAIFORD and E. L. HILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 174.
10. H. B. HENBEST, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4536.

Studies on Emulsions of Dichlorodiphenyl trichloroethane (D.D.T.) in presence of Some Adjuvants

S. D. SHUKLA & KRANTI KUMAR

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 18 February 1974; revised 8 August 1974; accepted 14 August 1974

IN continuation with the previous work^{7,8} on the stability coefficients of emulsions of insecticides and fungicides, it was considered desirable and useful to extend the study to Dichlorodiphenyl trichloroethane $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{Cl}_5$ (commonly nicknamed D.D.T.) which has been used as insecticide within recent years. It is of outstanding effectiveness against the Japanese beetle, codling moth etc.

Kennedy³ showed that mosquitoes are repelled by the effect of contacting D.D.T. treated surfaces. Having a low melting point D.D.T. itself can not be made into a fine powder for mixture directly with a dust diluent. The best way of its use as a spray is in the form of emulsion.

Experimental

The gums were purified by the methods as described by Mukherjee and Shukla⁴ in their earlier work on gums. The emulsions were prepared at 30° by King and Mukherjee's¹ method using fixed concentration of D.D.T. alone and then by adding fixed amounts of gums, china-clay, Fuller's earth and sodium oleate keeping the ratio of the oil (kerosene or olive oil) to water as 20 : 80 so that the emulsions produced were not very viscous and could be sprayed easily for practical purposes. The size frequency analysis was done immediately and on regular intervals of time of the ageing emulsions. The stability coefficients were computed from the data on specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares as described by Mukherjee and Shukla^{5,6}. Emulsion type (o/w or w/o) was determined by the dye solubility method². It was found that all emulsions produced were of o/w type.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the data of table No. 1 that D.D.T. alone is not capable of producing good and stable emulsions with either of the oils used below the concentration of 5% of the emulsifier. However, olive oil gave a somewhat stable emulsion, stability coefficient being of the order of 0.75. Most of the oil was separated only in one week's storage time.

TABLE 1—DATA FOR 20% KEROSENE & OLIVE OIL EMULSIONS

Emulsion no.	Agent	Graphically determined initial Specific Area $\sigma \times 10^3$	Stability coefficient ($k \times 10^3$)
KEROSENE OIL EMULSIONS			
51	5% D.D.T. alone	Broken immediately	
52	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Dhak Gum	14.79	211.28
53	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Dhak Gum	13.80	125.45
54	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Bel Gum	14.12	61.39
55	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Bel Gum	2.69	1.96
56	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Katira Gum	7.58	4.92
57	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Katira Gum	5.75	3.05
58	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Fuller's Earth	10.71	46.56
59	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Fuller's Earth	10.00	19.60
60	5% D.D.T.+0.5% China clay	7.94	5.75
61	5% D.D.T.+0.1% China clay	6.16	0.53
62	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Sodium oleate	25.12	9.13
OLIVE OIL EMULSIONS			
63	5% D.D.T. alone	5.25	0.75
64	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Dhak Gum	13.33	190.42
65	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Dhak Gum	13.80	138.00
66	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Bel Gum	7.07	88.37
67	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Bel Gum	9.33	44.42
68	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Katira Gum	10.59	46.04
69	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Katira Gum	10.23	8.90
70	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Fuller's Earth	8.32	83.20
71	5% D.D.T.+0.5% Fuller's Earth	6.76	23.31
72	5% D.D.T.+0.5% China Clay	Broken immediately	
73	5% D.D.T.+0.1% China clay	Broken immediately	
74	5% D.D.T.+0.1% Sodium oleate	18.19	5.21

Addition of 0.1% sodium oleate to the above series of emulsions produced somewhat more stable emulsions. Kerosene oil produced more stable and much finer emulsion, the stability coefficients being

9.13 (kerosene oil) and 5.21 (olive oil) in the two cases.

Fine clays were listed as emulsifiers by Pickering⁹ in 1907. Yothers and Winston¹⁰ recommended kaolin and Fuller's earth as good substitutes for the soaps. It is evident from the studies of emulsions 58, 59, 70 and 71 of Table 1 that Fuller's earth in combination with D.D.T. gave very stable emulsions in case of kerosene oil being the internal phase. The stability coefficients being 46.56, 19.60 with different percentages of the clay. The emulsions with olive oil as internal phase are still more stable as the stability coefficient values are increased to 83.20 and 23.31 respectively. Fuller's earth combination gave finer emulsions (in case of kerosene oil) as compared to their counterpart olive oil emulsions.

China clay combinations with D.D.T. did not show much improvement so far as the stability coefficient and initial specific area values are concerned. Olive oil proved to be detrimental as emulsions at once broke after preparation.

Out of the three gums which have been used as adjuvants with D.D.T., Dhak Gum combination gave the most stable emulsions both in case of kerosene and olive oil as internal phases as can be seen from stability coefficient values of emulsion Nos. 52, 53, 64, 65 respectively. The dispersions in case of kerosene oil emulsions being much finer, a very large percentage of particles ranged between 1μ - 5μ .

Katira gum combination although increased the stability coefficient values as compared to D.D.T. alone, but out of the 3 gums used, this is the worst; it deteriorates rapidly on keeping; its emulsions are much coarse with respect to the other gum combinations.

It is clear from the above discussion that although D.D.T. alone can not produce very stable emulsions, very stable emulsions of o/w type can be prepared by combination of different adjuvants. The optimum quantity of the different adjuvants is 0.5%. The addition of sodium oleate, clays and different Indian gums increased the stability of the emulsions appreciably. In presence of gums most stable emulsions are produced, which are otherwise unstable. The increase in the stability is probably due to greater adsorption of the adjuvants at the dimeric interface, thereby, facilitating the formation of a highly hydrated membrane around the oil globules.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their gratefulness to Professor Dr. Ram Gopal, Head of Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow, for providing laboratory facilities and to State C.S.I.R. (U.P.) and also to U.G.C. for the financial assistance.

References

1. A. KING and L. N. MUKHERJEE, *J. Chem. Soc. Ind.*, 1939, 58, 243.
2. E. A. HAUSER and J. E. LYNN, "Experiments in Colloid Chemistry", McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1940, p. 129.

3. J. S. KENNEDY, *Bull. Entomol. Res.*, 1947, **37**, 593.
4. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 123.
5. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 805.
6. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 177; 1967, **30**, 187.
7. S. D. SHUKLA and KRANTI KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **58**, 726.
8. S. D. SHUKLA and KRANTI KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
9. S. U. PICKERING, Emulsions, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 2001.
10. W. W. YOTHEBS and J. R. WINSTON, *Agr. Research.*, 1925, **31**, 59.

Metal Chelates of Lanthanoids. A Spectrophotometric study using Bromopyrogallol Red as a Ligand

MOHAN S. JOG*, SUBHASH C. PANDE**, VASANT L. SHAH† & SATENDRA P. SANGAL‡

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur

Manuscript received 14 May 1974; accepted 20 August 1974

BROMOPYROGALLOL Red (abbrev. BPGR) has been observed to possess very interesting chromogenic properties. It forms coloured chelates with a number of metal ions¹. Aluminium, gallium and indium form a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex² while titanium, zirconium and hafnium form a 1 : 1 chelate with this reagent³. Thorium and uranium⁴, molybdenum and tungsten⁵ also form 1 : 1 chelate with this reagent. Herrington and Steed⁶ have used the reagent in the determination of rare-earths while Suk⁷ reported the determination of lanthanum under similar conditions. It was thought to be of interest to study the chelates of BPGR with Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Er. In the present communication, the results on the composition, formation constants and other characteristics of the chelates formed between BPGR and the metals mentioned above are reported.

Experimental

Instruments : Hydrogen ion concentration of the solutions was adjusted by using a Leeds and Northrup pH meter with a glass calomel electrode of the same make. The pH meter was standardized by standard buffers supplied along with the instrument. For spectro-photometric studies a Beckman model B spectrophotometer operated on 115 V/50 cycles AC mains was used. 10 mm thickness matched glass cells were used for solutions.

Conditions of experiment : All experiments were carried out in a thermostatically controlled air conditioned room maintained at 25° ± 1°.

Chemicals : Solutions of Bromopyrogallol Red were prepared by dissolving suitable amounts of the reagent in 40% alcohol and the final volume was

made up with double distilled water. Solutions of rare-earths were prepared by dissolving the requisite amounts of the metal oxides or chlorides in minimum quantity of HCl and then making up the volume with double distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Effect of time and pH on an aqueous solution of BPGR :

Freshly prepared solutions were used. The colour of the dye varies with change in pH. The change in λ_{max} of the dye with variation in pH is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1
EFFECT OF pH ON THE AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF BPGR

pH	Wavelength of maximum absorbance (nm)
0.1—0.05	480
0.5—3.2	430
3.2—4.5	570
4.5—8.0	580

Effect of pH on the formation of the chelates :

The chelates of the metal ions studied with BPGR are formed within a limited range of pH. The results are included in Table 2.

TABLE 2
EFFECT OF pH ON THE FORMATION OF CHELATES

Chelate	pH range of stability	λ _{max} of Chelate (nm)
Sc(III)-BPGR	3.3—6.0	590
Y(III)-BPGR	3.8—6.5	680
La(III)-BPGR	4.1—8.0	720
Ce(III)-BPGR	3.8—7.0	690
Pr(III)-BPGR	4.0—7.0	690
Nd(III)-BPGR	4.0—9.1	690
Sm(III)-BPGR	4.0—8.0	690
Eu(III)-BPGR	3.9—7.0	690
Gd(III)-BPGR	5.5—8.0	690
Tb(III)-BPGR	5.5—8.1	690
Dy(III)-BPGR	5.6—8.9	690
Ho(III)-BPGR	5.6—8.8	680
Er(III)-BPGR	5.0—8.5	680

The table indicates that study of all the elements can be made at pH 6.0.

Nature of the complexes formed :

Several mixtures containing metal ion and BPGR in the ratio 0 : 1, 1 : 0.5, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 were prepared by keeping the total volume 25 ml in each case. After mixing the metal solution with BPGR solution at the same pH, it was observed that the pH falls. Hence 5.0 ml of sodium acetate-acetic buffer was added to maintain the required pH. Absorbance readings were noted between

*V.R.C.E., Nagpur, **G.S.I., Nagpur, † Prapat College, Amalner, ‡ L.I.T., Nagpur.